

MAY
2025

PRESS RELEASE

Ljubljana, Slovenia | 27-29 May 2025

MICROBETECH 2025 MARKS A SUCCESSFUL MILESTONE IN MICROBIAL INNOVATION

The **MicrobeTech 2025** event, co-organised by the **BIOSYSMO** and **BIOREM** projects, has officially concluded with great success at the Jožef Stefan Institute (JSI) in Ljubljana, Slovenia. Held from 27 to 29 May 2025, the event brought together researchers, industry professionals, and students to explore cutting-edge advances in microbial-based solutions for environmental remediation.

The three-day event featured a public workshop, a poster session, an intensive summer school and internal project meetings, with nearly 100 participants attending both in person and online. Attendees had the opportunity to engage with over 20 expert presenters, representing leading institutions and organisations across Europe. Topics ranged from microbial viability and phytoremediation to genome-scale modelling and field applications.

A highlight of the event was the poster session, which showcased more than 20 research posters from researchers and students. During this day the two poster award winners were announced. More information can be found below:

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- **Engineering Microbial Consortia to Boost Phytoremediation of Mixed Pollutants in Estuarine Ecosystems** (Margarida Pereira, Joana P. Fernandes, Dmitrii Deev, Maja Zupan, Tomaž Rijavec, Aleš Lapanje, C. Marisa R. Almeida, Ana P. Mucha)
- **Optimising metal phytoremediation by *Phragmites australis* through PGPR-based microbial consortia and inoculation techniques** (Alberto Soto-Cañas, Ana Arnaiz, Aqib Hassan Ali Khan, Elena Clavel-Millan, Andrea Martín-Pablo, Carlos Rad, Blanca Velasco-Arroyo, Rocío Barros and José Carlos Castilla-Alcántara)

Overall, MicrobeTech 2025 provided a platform for sharing project results, exchanging knowledge, and building synergies between the **BIOSYSMO**, **BIOREM**, and other relevant projects including **NYPHE**, **MIBIREM**, **TRIBIOME**, and **MySoil**, among others. With the aim of strengthening collaboration across disciplines, the event demonstrated the growing relevance of microbial technologies in addressing environmental challenges and promoting a circular bioeconomy.

More details, including speaker information, can be found here:
<https://www.biosysmo.eu/event-speakers>

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We would like to extend our special thanks to **JSI, IDENER, ICCRAM** (University of Burgos) and **EXELISIS**, forming the scientific and organisational committee.

BIOSYSMO and **BIOREM** partners also extend their gratitude to all attendees and speakers for making MicrobeTech 2025 a remarkable success.

